

**Some Opportunities and Challenges
of
Teacher Professional Development Programme:
A Case of the Secondary Schools in Menchyayem Rural Municipality**

A Mini Research

Submitted to

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Submitted by

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this mini research entitled Some Opportunities and Challenges of Teacher Professional Development Programme: A Case of the Secondary Schools in Menchyayem Rural Municipality is my own and original research work, and it will become a part of permanent collection of Research Management Cell, Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta.

I understand that my signature below authorities release of my research work to any readers upon request.

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Evaluation and Approval

This mini research entitled **Some Opportunities and Challenges of Teacher Professional Development Programme: A Case of the Secondary Schools in Menchhayem Rural Municipality** was carried out by Ambika Prasad Poudel, a lecturer of English education, from 16th January, 2022 to 15th April, 2022 on behalf of Research Management Cell (RMC), Dhankuta Multiple Campus, Dhankuta. This mini research report prepared and presented by Mr Poudel has been evaluated and approved by following evaluation and approval committee.

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Abstract

This study entitled **Some Opportunities and Challenges of Teacher Professional Development Programme: A Case of the Secondary Schools in Menchyayem Rural Municipality**, was a wonderful experience for me of carrying out a research work in one of the more relevant issues of present day world. The main objective of this research was to study the existing TPD (teacher professional development) status of the secondary schools, and to explore the opportunities and challenges appeared in the TPD program implemented in the secondary school education in Nepal.

This study was guided by constructivist research paradigm that characterizes subjectivity and multiple realities. It adopted qualitative approach of research to study the social phenomena, “The opportunities and challenges of teacher professional development programme”. The Headmaster from all the secondary schools of Menchyayem Rural Municipality were the informants to help fill in the observational check list, one of the research tools used in the study. Likewise the secondary school senior teachers from all the schools were other participants in the study to share their ideas and experiences of teacher professional development process, particularly, the opportunities and challenges they experienced. The quantitative data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and thematic analysis method was used to analyze the qualitative data in the study.

The study found that the TPD status of the secondary schools is less satisfactory. None of the schools have excellent status. More remarkably, they do not have even medium status, most of them have weak standard. The schools were able to perform TPD related activities such as participating in the training, taking part in subject-members discussion; and getting some support for managing teaching-learning materials. They are weak to perform the activities such as carrying out research work and getting them published, conducting observational tours, and rewarding the best performing teachers. Lack of adequate budget and inadequate administrative monitoring and supervision are some of the major factors affecting TPD. Therefore, it is important to address the challenges caused by these factors at both government and local level to make overall improvement in the existing situation of professional development of the teachers in the secondary schools.

Abbreviations

CD	Compact Disk
CDC	Curriculum Development Center
e.g.	exempli gratia (=for example)
EFA	Education for All
ERO	Education Review Office
etc,	et cetera (=and so on)
i.e.	id est (=that is)
INGOs	International Non-Governmental Organizations
ITTP	In service Teacher Training Programme
MOE	Ministry of Education
MOES	Ministry of Education and Sports
MSS	Malaysian Smart School
NCED	National Center for Educational Development
NESP	National Educational System Plan
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
OCE	Office of the Controller of Examinations
p.	page
SCPS	Student Centered Problem Solving
SESP	Secondary Education Support Plan
SLT	Social Learning Theory
SSRP	School Sector Reform Plan
TEP	Teacher Education Project
TPA	Teaching Performance Assessment
TPCK	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge

TPD	Teacher Professional Development
US	United States
VCD	Visual Compact Disk
WTP	Whole Teacher Approach

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

Background

Teacher professional development (TPD) is one of the essential components of quality education and education reform. An ideal education reform process necessitates improvements not only on the physical infrastructures of the educational institutions, but also on the professional quality of the teachers working in those institutions. In fact, teachers are the key persons affecting quality of education, and they influence the success or failure of the whole education system (OECD, 2002). Teachers have direct impact on the students' progress, growth and development. Therefore, increasing the number of highly qualified professional teachers has become the main focus of an education system nowadays in both developed and developing countries, and a greater emphasis has been given to promoting professional development of the teachers.

TPD, simply, is a process that brings an ongoing change in the quality of the teachers which makes them professional. It is a process in which the teachers master knowledge and skills essential for professional practices to promote teaching career (Hoyle, 1980). To Perry (1980), TPD is the personal growth in the professional life of the teachers, it is the enhancement and improvement of their skills and confidence, and their expertise of disciplinary knowledge with constant update. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] defines professional development of teacher as 'the activities that develop an individual's skills, knowledge, expertise and other characteristics as a teacher' (OECD, 2009, p. 49).

According to Jiang (2017), TPD consists of three important aspects related to teaching career: (i) teacher training (that improves classroom teaching skills and techniques), (ii) teacher education (that aims to perfect teachers' theoretical knowledge), and (iii) teachers' development (that focuses on improving teachers' practical teaching level and cognitive level). To be brief, TPD is process of preparing better quality teachers enhancing their professional life and overall development which plays significant role for ensuring educational quality. It is an on-going activity during the professional life of the teachers that includes training, practice, feedback , self-observation, and follow-up support.

TPD, particularly, is concerned with enhancing teaching career and preparing professional teachers. Becoming a professional teacher means acquiring specialized training, knowledge and expertise to provide services in the field of teaching. A professional teacher is one who is experienced with specialized skills rather than one who is involved in an economic activity to make a living. The professional teachers involve themselves expanding their knowledge and skills based on research and issues in teaching, take on new roles and responsibilities, and engage in self-reflection and evaluation (Richards, .& Farrell, 2005). Professional teachers "not only have a good knowledge or expertise, but also organizing capacity for teaching activities, control capacity for discussing teaching, and guiding capacity

for exploring teaching” (Jiang, 2017, p 2). Thus, TPD is crucial for not only enhancing teachers’ professional life and improving the quality of teachers, but also for ensuring quality education and education reform.

The concept of teachers’ professional qualification was instrumented in Nepal in 1971 with the introduction of National Educational System Plan (NESP). After 22 years, National Center for Educational Development (NCED) was established under Ministry of Education with a view to enhance teachers’ professional development giving priority to in service teacher training programme (ITTP). The ITTP was extended to TPD programme with the implementation of School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP) 2009-2016, which gave a high emphasis to TPD training for enhancing teachers’ knowledge, competency and capacity (MOE, 2009). The main objective of TPD training was to refresh and strengthen the knowledge and skills of the teachers in order to improve their classroom instruction and student learning achievement.

TPD has been supposed to be a key mechanism for bringing improvement in classroom pedagogy and students’ outcomes. Teachers are more likely to gain better subject knowledge improved pedagogical skills through TPD training. In context of the completion of the implementation of SSRP (2009-2016) with its TPD programme which had an aim ‘to enhance teachers’ qualifications and professional competencies to better facilitate students learning processes’ in Nepal (MOE, 2009), the exploration of the issues related to TPD, and the evaluation of TPD programme has been a common concern to the educators and researchers at present.

Statement of the Problem

TPD, at present, has been one of the important concern to the educational institutions in the world. The government of Nepal has realized teacher preparation and teachers’ professional development as the key factor for education reform (MOE, 2009). Consequently, the government has prioritized mandatory training requirements and regular updates of the teachers. Likewise, several plans and programs such as NESP, SSRP, and Secondary Education Support Programme (SESP) have been implemented and a large amount of money has been invested for TPD in the secondary school education in Nepal. However, the number of the empirical studies that evaluate and explore the effect of such investment on TPD programme is quite a few. Moreover, there is still a lack of the empirical study that reveals the real picture of the TPD status of the secondary schools, and analyzes the opportunities and challenges of TPD programme in the secondary schools as the outcome of such programmes in Nepal. Research studies on the periphery of this research gap can be worthwhile.

Research Questions

This study aims at investigating the issue related to the TPD standard in the secondary schools in Nepal. Followings will be the research questions of this study:

- (a) What is the status of TPD in the secondary schools in Nepal?

- (b) What are the opportunities and challenges of TPD Programme in the secondary schools?

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to depict the exiting TPD position in the secondary schools, and the effects of the TPD programme to the teachers in the secondary schools in Nepal. The specific objectives of the study will be as follows:

- (a) To find out the current TPD status of the secondary schools in Nepal based on the TPD indicators, and
- (b) To explore the opportunities and challenges of TPD programme in the secondary schools.

Significance of the Study

TPD is one of the widely concerned subject matters worldwide because it is one of the crucial factors for quality education and education reform. It has been a more important issue for some decades in Nepal too. This study depicts and evaluates the TPD position of the secondary schools in Nepal and analyzes the opportunities and challenges of TPD programme in the secondary schools. Thus, this study will be worthwhile to develop an insight of the teachers, students, and educators about TPD. Moreover, this study will give a guideline to the government, and other NGOs and INGOs who need to make further plans and policies related to teacher education and teacher professional development.

Delimitations

The researcher makes some choices and decisions about the inclusionary matters in the research study, which are the delimitations. Followings were the delimitations in this study:

- (a) The study included the secondary schools of only one local level of only one district of Koshi zone as the study site.
- (b) Only the four secondary schools of Menchyayem rural municipality, the four Headmasters, and four secondary level senior teachers from those schools were involved in the study.
- (c) The study was concentrated on only the evaluation of TPD standard and analyze the opportunities and challenges of TPD programme experienced by the teachers in the secondary schools.

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

The terms that carry the important concept in the study are the key terms. Some of the key terms and their definitions in this study have been presented below:

Teacher professional development (TPD): Teacher professional development (TPD) is an ongoing process in the professional life of the teachers that includes practice,

feedback, training, and follow-up support for mastering knowledge, and skills essential for professional practices.

Education reform: Education reform is a process of restructuring the educational standard including improvements in infrastructures, teaching methodologies and administrative process.

In service teacher training programme (ITTP): In service teacher training programme is a programme in course of the teachers' employment in which they are engaged in training and further education to refresh and upgrade their professional knowledge, skills, and practices.

Chapter Plan/Organization of the Study Report

This research report has been divided into five chapters. The first chapter 'Introduction' has discussed the background context, and has included mainly the statement of the problem, research objectives, significance, and the delimitations of the study. Likewise, the second chapter 'Review of literature and conceptual framework' has reviewed the related literature to widen the concepts of the phenomenon, and to develop theoretical and conceptual framework. The third chapter 'Methodology' dealt with the research paradigm, design, method, research tools; and sampling and data analysis procedures of the study. Similarly, the fourth chapter 'Results and analyses' has dealt with the presentation of the results and their interpretation and analysis. Finally, the last chapter 'Summary, conclusion and recommendations' has summarized the whole study and drawn conclusions and recommendations based on the findings.

CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A number of studies and research works are available that explore different issues related to TPD. I have reviewed some of the more relevant literature thematically under different sub-headings in this section.

Professional Teacher and TPD Process

A profession, simply, is an occupation, which requires specialized training or knowledge, and a high degree of education and expertise in the concerned area. A professional teacher has specialization and a specific set of pedagogical skills. Ur (2002) makes a comparison among a professional, a lay, an amateur, a technician, and an academic person. To her, a lay is a person who does not possess certain skills and knowledge, and does not belong to any specified professional group while an amateur does an action well or badly, but s/he does it for fun. Ur views, a technician person is a skillful craftsman though s/he is not able to articulate, relate and innovate skills. In contrast, an academic person is occupied in thinking and researching and acts in order to refine thinking though s/he is not an immediate agent of real world change while a professional person is occupied to improve real-time action, and is an immediate agent of real-world change. To Ur, 'professional' person is someone who performs a certain function with some degree of expertise. She opines professional teachers are responsible autonomous committed community who learn and publish. According to Richards and Farrell (2005, p vii), for professional development, the teachers need to take part in the activities such as:

- (i) engaging in self-reflection and evaluation
- (ii) developing specialized knowledge and skills about many aspects of teaching
- (iii) expanding their knowledge base about research, theory, and issues in teaching
- (iv) taking on new roles and responsibilities, such as supervisor or mentor teacher, teacher-researcher, or materials writer
- (v) developing collaborative relationships with other teachers

Thus, the professional teachers are responsible persons who regularly update themselves being involved in self-evaluation and collaboration. They possess a high degree of expertise, knowledge and skills required in teaching career.

Professional teachers are always engage in TPD process which is ongoing activity of learning. Ackerman (2006) carried out a study entitled 'The learning never stops: Lesson from military child development centers for teacher professional development' to examine the effect of TPD training on teachers learning. The study used a qualitative interview method, and 13 caregivers and 8 training and curriculum specialists from the mid-Atlantic region of the U.S were taken as the sample. The study concluded that quality teacher training was beneficial for

the teachers to improve learning, However, it was found that most states had minimal educational requirements for the teachers and they faced barriers in accessing effective professional development.

The teachers needs need to be addressed by the professional development activities. Othman (2005) conducted a study entitled 'Managing teacher professional development in changing times: A study of in-service teacher professional development in Malaysian smart school' to explore in-service professional development activities and their impact on the implementation. The study had used semi-structured interview data to collect experiences from teachers and school administrators (principals and senior assistants) of Malaysian Smart School (MSS). It was concluded that the TPD activities should focus the demands and needs of the market rather than giving priority on the values and morals of teacher professionalism in this age of world globalization

TPD Indicators and TPD Activities

There are several indicators of teacher professional development. Education review office (ERO), under Government of Nepal, Ministry of Education identifies six indicators of teachers' professional development in the 'work performance audit tool-2020' they developed. Those TPD indicators (ERO, 2020, p.12) are:

- (i) Creative and collaborative work (workshop, seminar, project work, subject teachers meeting etc)
- (ii) Capacity building work(capacity building training, resource class conduction)
- (iii) Journal, bulletin, wall post, article publication
- (iv) Study visit (inter-school visit, model school visit, geographical visit)
- (v) Learning/study material management (daily/monthly, half yearly/yearly newspaper)
- (vi) Teacher encouragement/reward

Richards and Farrell (2005) identify five major areas of teacher professional development. They are: (a) subject matter knowledge, (b) pedagogical expertise, (c) self-awareness, (d) understanding of learners, curriculum and materials, and (e) career advancement. Different activities are needed to be performed by the teachers for their overall professional development. Such activities can be categorized into four types (Richards & Farrell, 2005, p. 14):

- (i) Individual activities (self-monitoring, journal writing, critical incidents, teaching portfolios, action research)
- (ii) One-to-one activities (peer coaching, peer observation, critical friendships, action research, critical incidents, team teaching)
- (iii) Group activities (case studies, action research, journal writing, teacher support groups)

(iv) Institutional activities (workshops, action research, teacher support groups)

To be brief, TPD includes both individual and group activities such as self- updating activities, creative and collaborative activities, learning resource management activities, study visit activities, and publication activities.

TPD Plans and Projects in Nepal

Different national education plans and projects have been made in Nepal with the aim of quality growth of education, and TPD has been included as one of the essential components in those plans and programmes. Among them, National Education System Plan (NESP)-1971, Teacher Education Project (TEP)-2001, Secondary Education Support Project (SESP)-2003, and School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP)-2009 had given more emphasis on TPD as a part of education reform.

NESP-1971 aimed at bringing a drastic change in the existing disorganized education system of that time. NESP identified several weaknesses of the existing education and pointed out that shortage of trained teachers, standard textbook, and physical aids in the educational institutions were some of the main constraints for the development of modern education system (MOE, 1971). Therefore, it gave more emphasis on teacher training and on the improvement of the standard of teacher training for bringing quality in education. The plan also made a provision for in service training, and teacher training scholarships for enhancing professional development of the teachers.

TEP-2001 was implemented to bring improvement in the poor quality of teaching-learning, and low student achievements. The TEP aimed at strengthening teacher training infrastructure, and establishing an effective and sustainable teacher education (ADB, 2012). The project had four major components: building institutional capacity, developing teacher education and teaching-learning materials, providing training to teachers, and educating teachers to better serve the needs of girls and other disadvantaged groups (ADB, 2012). In this way, the project targeted professional development of the teachers through teacher training and learning materials development.

SESP-2003 was implemented by the Department of Education under the ministry of education, with the support of the key educational agencies such as the National Centre for Education Development (NCED), Curriculum Development Center (CDC), and Office of the Controller of Examinations (OCE). The Project had five components: (i) enhancing teacher effectiveness by improving teacher training curricula and providing teacher training in core subjects; (ii) developing new secondary curricula and textbooks in the core subjects; (iii) improving the student assessment system; (iv) providing learning materials, science equipment, and civil works for school laboratories and buildings extension; and (v) strengthening the capacity of the Ministry of Education and Sports (MOES) in planning, management, and benefit monitoring and evaluation (ADB, 2004). Teacher training, an important part of TPD, was given a greater priority by the project.

SSRP-2009 was implemented as a continuation of on-going programmes such as Education for All (EFA), SESP, and Teacher performance Assessment (TPA). SSRP aimed at strengthening education reform giving emphasis on the restructuring of school education, improvement on quality of education, and institutionalization of performance accountability (MOE, 2009). Professional development of the teachers was one of the major components of SSRP. It gave the highest priority in teacher preparation and in the quality and efficiency of the teachers. The main objective was to enhance teachers' qualifications and professional competencies to better facilitate students learning process (MOE, 2009).

Approaches to Teacher Professional development

Discussing a conceptual framework for in-service professional development, Chen and McCray (2012) propose 'Whole Teacher Approach (WTP)', which, they claim to be significantly different from the traditional approach to TPD. They argue that the traditional approach is concerned with the teachers' acquisition of knowledge and skills, while the whole teacher approach stresses all aspects including Attitudes (A), Knowledge (K), and Practice (P) for promoting TPD. They write that to constitute high-quality in-service PD, a large body of literature following traditional approach specify the factors such as: (i) using an ongoing process instead of one-shot workshop, (ii) emphasizing collaborative participation rather than working individually, (iii) tailoring specific needs in training instead of covering general goals, and (iv) providing opportunities for knowledge construction to classroom practice rather than target knowledge transmission. They argue that these factors (mentioned above) are concerned with how teacher training is delivered, but not with providing an overarching understanding of 'what works' to design and analysis their efforts that support their professional activities. Therefore, they emphasize the need of a conceptual framework that acknowledges the complex course of teacher development and provides a basis for setting goals and strategies, and evaluating outcomes. In the framework, they include three major components of teacher development: attitudes, knowledge, and practice.

The WTP presents all social, emotional, cognitive and behavioral aspects of teacher growth simultaneously including attitudes, knowledge, and practice as the major components. It has been claimed that teachers' attitude affects their thinking, motivation, and behavior; and it mediates the process of skill development and classroom implementation. Therefore, it is crucial to promote positive attitude by means of the activities such as establishing a community of the teachers, providing them with familiar teaching books, and building their strength in professional development sessions. Another factor of WTP is 'knowledge' which refers to both content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge of the teachers. WTP emphasizes the pedagogical content knowledge which comprises of what, who and how aspects of contents to be delivered. The approach takes improvements in the 'classroom practice' as the ultimate goal of TPD. Developing new practices supports the teachers in both knowledge construction and knowledge internalization process.

Discussing about the rapid changes in the field of language teaching (such as in the educational paradigm, in texts and curriculum, and in students' need), Richards and Farrell, (2005) opine that teachers need regular opportunities to update their professional knowledge and skills. The language teachers need to keep them up to date with recent development in the field, regularly update and evaluate their teaching skills, and they need to take on new teaching assignments. They also need to plan workshops and other professional development activities, to present papers at seminars or at conferences, and serve as the mentors to novel teachers. Likewise, they need to be able to take part in: (i) engaging in self-reflection and evaluation, (ii) developing specialized knowledge and skills about many aspects of teaching, (iii) expanding their knowledge base about research, theory, and issues in teaching, (iv) taking on new roles and responsibilities, such as supervisor, teacher-researcher, or materials writer, and (v) developing collaborative relationships with other teachers

Richards and Farrell, (2005) examine eleven different procedures as an approach to teacher development reflecting the combined experiences of the teachers in North America and the Asia Pacific region. The eleven procedures of the teacher development approach include:

- (i) Action research
- (ii) Self-monitoring
- (iii) Teacher support groups
- (iv) Keeping a teaching journal
- (v) Peer observation
- (vi) Workshops Teaching portfolios
- (vii) Analyzing critical incidents
- (viii) Case analysis
- (ix) Peer coaching
- (x) Team teaching

Implications of Literature Review and Research Gap

There are several literature available that explore the different issues of TPD. The review of literature helped to develop concept and widen the knowledge of the phenomenon. The review gave an insight to understand and analyze about different aspects and issues related to TPD. However, the literature based on the context of 'TPD in Nepalese school education' are quite a few. Moreover, there is still lack of the comparative study evaluating TPD standard of secondary schools based on the TPD indicators in Nepal. This study makes an attempt to fulfil this research gap.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework that will guide this study is social learning theory (SLT) proposed by Albert Bandura in 1977. SLT is an approach for analyzing human thoughts and behaviors that are influenced by observation and experiences. It emphasizes the central role played by self-regulatory processes resulted from observational behaviors in psychological functioning (Bandura, 1977). This framework explains the human behavior in terms of continuous interaction among cognitive, behavioral, and environmental determinants that appear in teacher professional development.

SLT is a theoretical approach that is useful to describe and explain the phenomenon of teachers' professional learning (Watson, 2013). Teacher professional development includes both cognitive aspects (i. e., changes in teachers' belief and knowledge) and social aspects (i. e., learning through participation) of learning (Borko, 2004). In this regard, SLT provides an integrated view accounting for individual learning, cognitive aspects of learning, and social and participatory aspects of learning. SLT considers 'observation' as the important mechanism of learning and formation of individual knowledge (Lortie, 2002). In fact, the core component of SLT is learning through observation and mental modelling of observed behaviors. SLT assumes that mental modelling of observed behavior is consequently reflected in the construction of novel behavior (Watson, 2013). This observational behavior, the self-efficacy within SLT, has been found to be essential component in teacher development (Lortie, 2002) in which teachers (re)construct behaviors to implement in the classroom. This self-efficacy, an important sub-construct of SLT, has been widely used in theorizing teacher education. According to Bandura (1997), this self-efficacy reflects cognitive capacities and underlying skills of the teachers, such as confidence, motivation and willingness to innovate. It is believed that self-efficacy is related to positive teaching behaviors, which encourages teachers to use student centered problem solving (SCPS) approaches involving the students in discussion and collaboration for solving the tasks or problems. Thus, SLT is relevant to understand explain and analyze different aspects of TPD.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is the researcher's concept or understanding about the outline to explore the research problem. It is the researcher's scheme that includes research philosophy, research design, methods, and the key concepts that the researcher operationalizes to achieve the research objectives. According to Miles and Huberman (1994) a conceptual framework is an outline displaying the relationships among the concepts and assumptions that guide the research plan (p. 440).

Finding out the TPD status, and exploring the possibilities and challenges of TPD in the secondary schools is the main objective of this study. As shown in Figure 1, the study will be guided by the constructivist research paradigm. Similarly, the case study methods under qualitative research design will be adopted. Likewise, TPD status, and the possibilities and challenges of TPD in the secondary schools will be studied within the theoretical framework

of SLT. Finally, research conclusion will be drawn by analyzing the results.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

This section of the study deals with the research paradigm, research design, research methods and tools. It also discusses about the source of data, sampling and data analysis procedure, and the ethical consideration of the study.

Research Paradigm

A research paradigm in the research study is the philosophical belief of the researcher that guides him/her to undertake the study. Simply, it is the researcher's ideological stand to provide him/her with a framework for conducting a research. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005), a research paradigm is the philosophical stand of the researcher's ontological, epistemological, and methodological ideologies.

Among different philosophical worldviews existed in the field of research, the research paradigm that has guided this research study is constructivism. Constructivism always rejects that there is single and objective reality in any research or investigation (Mertens, 2010). The constructivists opine that every individual develops subjective meanings of his/her experiences, and this makes his/her understanding and interpretation of meaning of the events varied and multiple (Creswell, 2014). The constructivists' philosophical worldview has been adopted as the research paradigm to guide this study.

Research Design

According to Creswell (2009) a research design is the plan of a researcher that combines philosophy, strategy of inquiry, and specific methods and procedures to guide a research. Thus, a research design is blueprint showing the coordination of the elements needed to carry out a research. To Creswell (2014), qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods are the main categories of research designs used.

This study aims at depicting TPD status and analyzing the opportunities and challenges of TPD in the secondary schools in Nepal being guided by constructivist's philosophical guideline. To constructivists, reality is socially constructed and context dependent (Guba & Lincoln, 2005). Constructivists prefer qualitative designs in order to gain a detail understanding the participants' experiences in the society. For studying the issues related to TPD, I have chosen qualitative research design so as to understand the meaning of the social issues or events. According to Guba and Lincoln (2005), the constructivist paradigm is not anti-quantitative; and there are many opportunities for the naturalistic investigator to utilize quantitative data (p. 201). Thus, as suggested by Guba and Lincoln (2005, p. 201), I adopted both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection in this study.

Field of Study

The study site of this study is Menchyayem rural municipality of Terhathum district. Particularly, the smallest local government of Terhathum district, Menchyayem rural municipality, which could be the representative of all the local governments, was selected as the study site using purposive convenient sampling methods considering time, money and labor to be spent. The interpretivists prefer non-random purposive sampling methods in which the members/ items are selected intentionally, who/which in researcher's judgement can provide needed information (Creswell, 2012, Kumar, 2011). All the four secondary schools of Menchyayem rural municipality were included as the sample of population in the study of teacher professional development in the secondary schools. Those four schools were assigned pseudonyms as school-A, school-B, school-C, school-D for confidentiality and research ethics (Saunders, Kitzinger & Kitzinger, 2015).

Participants

This research aims at studying the secondary level teachers' experiences of the TPD activities. The Headmaster and the secondary school most senior teacher from each school were requested to be involved as the participants in the study. These participants were believed to share their experiences regarding the opportunities and challenges they experienced in their TPD process.

Research Methods and Tools

Guided by qualitative research design, observation and semi-structured interview methods were used in the study. These methods are considered to be more suitable in qualitative study to obtain in-depth information allowing the researcher to be an insider (Mertens, 2010). Likewise, observation checklist (see appendix-A) that was adapted from 'school performance audit tool' developed by ERO (ERO, 2020), and interview questionnaire (see Appendix-C) developed by the researcher were used as the research tools. Observation is a useful method that enables the researchers to understand the context or real situation; and to discover the things the participants might not like to communicate freely in the interview (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison 2005; Patton, 2002). The observation checklist and the questionnaire (see appendices) were prepared carefully well so as to receive required information. The observation checklist was used in each school to gather TPD related information from the Headmaster, and the semi structure interviews were carried out with the Headmaster and the most senior teacher of each school for about half an hour each. The interviews were recorded by using the recording devices for further use.

This study used observation checklist, and semi-structure interview as the research tools. A standard observation checklist 'the work performance audit tool for secondary school' ascertained by Education Review Office (ERO) was adapted as the research tool to understand about the TPD standard of the schools (see Appendix-B). Likewise, a questionnaire for the semi-structured interview with the secondary school teachers was also used as the research

tool. Besides these tools, the researcher's observation of the school was also utilized for collecting the exact detail of the TPD situation.

Source of Data

This study used primarily the primary data related to the TPD activities, and the opportunities and challenges of TPD in the secondary schools using the survey checklist, and semi structure interviews as the research tools. Likewise, the secondary sources of data such as books, articles, documents, school records were also be used for collecting fact and information, and for reviewing the literature and interpreting the results.

Sampling Procedure

The convenient purposive non-random sampling methods was used to select the research site and sample. As the research site, the smallest district 'Terhathum' of Koshi zone, and one of the smallest local level of Terhathum district 'Menchyayem rural municipality' was selected purposively. The smallest one was selected because the smaller one is easier from economical in terms of time, money and labor needed; and even if the district or local level is small, it could be a representative of the existing components and features of other districts or a local levels. All the four secondary schools of the Menchyayem rural municipality were chosen purposefully as the sample schools. Likewise, the Headmaster , and the most senior secondary school teacher of the selected secondary schools were the informants in the study.

Data Collection Procedure

In the process of the collection of data, the researcher visited the selected secondary schools and build up rapport with the Headmaster in each school. The researcher clarified the purpose and objectives of the project study and asked for permission for data collection from the school. The researcher took consents from the secondary school senior teacher in each school, who helped providing required data. In the data collection process, the researcher filled in the survey checklist in co-operation with the Headmaster of each secondary school. While filling in the checklist the researcher asked for the supporting proof for the data/information provided. Likewise, a semi-structured interview was conducted with each secondary level school senior teacher of the schools to understand and receive the information related to the opportunities and challenges they encountered in the process of their professional development.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

In this study, the data collected through observation checklist were presented in the tables. The criteria determined in the 'performance audit tool' developed by ERO (ERO, 2020) were adapted to be used to evaluate the TPD standard of the schools; and the results were described, analyzed and interpreted. The descriptive statistics, particularly, percentage and average were used in the analysis and interpretation.

On the other hand, guided by qualitative research design, thematic data analysis was

adopted to analyze the qualitative data in this study. Thematic analysis is one of the widely used methods of analyzing qualitative data for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within data. (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Maguire and Delahunt 2017). To Lapadat (2010), thematic analysis is a process of managing data, organizing and summarizing them, and presenting their interpretation. In this study, the information received from the respondents through semi-structure interviews were transcribed, and were read and re-read to have their clear understanding. Then, they were segmented, and categorized to generate themes. Finally, the meanings of the themes were interpreted in relation to the theoretical framework and comparing them with past literature. The interpretation also incorporated the facts collected using observation checklist and personal reflections of my teaching experiences.

Trustworthiness /Validity

Trustworthiness is understood as the quality of a work that measures what is intended to measure. According to Patton (2002), trustworthiness is the ‘rigor’ which combines the quality aspects such as transferability, credibility, dependability, and confirmability. To maintain transferability, thick description of the classroom context was presented in this study. Likewise, use of the extracts of the participants and member checking helped improve credibility (Creswell, 2014).

Ethical Consideration

Research ethics are the research conduct of the researcher related to the research values. These are the research codes of conduct such as authorship and attribution of credit, taking permission from the institution and consent from the participants, respecting the participants' confidential, and so on. In this research study, I took permission from the Headmasters and consents from the senior teachers of the selected secondary schools to collect data related to the phenomenon. I was much careful not to shake the data collected in their analysis and interpretation. I have carefully gave credit for ownership of the resources—books, articles, theses etc. All the participants were treated equally, and I was careful not to harm them and not to disclose their confidentiality.

CHAPTER IV: RESULT ANALYSES AND INTERPRETATION

This section deals with the findings of the study gained through the observation and interviews. The analysis and interpretation of the findings regarding the issue ‘TPD status in the secondary schools’ have been presented in the Tables, and is interpreted; and regarding ‘the opportunities and challenges in TPD process’ have been discussed thematically, and have been presented in the sub-headings to come.

TPD status in the schools

The TPD status in the school, particularly, the position of the schools regarding the TPD activities was studied using the observation checklist adapted from ERO (ERO, 2020). In the checklist there were included seven TPD indicators, detail of the TPD activities, and criteria of TPD level determination. The Tables below present all such information including the TPD level/score of the four schools; i.e., TPD performance evaluation of the schools.

Table 1: TPD Performance Evaluation of School A

S N	Indicators of TPD	Detail of TPD activities performed in the school	TPD level/ School score				Criteria of TPD level/standard determination
			0	1	2	3	
01	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teachers’ participation on training for PD ✓ ○ Conduction of training and workshop ✓ ○ Opportunity for further education (study leave, non-payment leave etc.) X ○ Visit to other schools ✓ ○ Research in group or individual ✓ ○ Learning materials for PD, their regularity and study ✓ ○ Meeting and discussion of the subject teachers ✓ ○ Writing and publication related to PD X 				3	0 None of the activities of the list performed 1 At least one of the activities performed 2 Two to four of the activities performed 3 More than four of the activities performed
02	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers involved in constructive work -12 ○ Detail of the constructive work (e.g., seminar ✓, workshop ✓, project work ✓, journal X, magazine X, 			2		0 If none of the teachers involved 1 If less than 25% of the teachers involved

		article writing X, subject teacher committee ✓)				2 If 25 to 50% of the teachers involved 3 If more than 50% of the teachers involved
03	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teacher involved in Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school last year X ○ Not organized 	0			0 Not organized 1 Less than 25% of the teachers involved in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers involved in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers involved in such activities
04	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine published by the school in last two years X ○ Not published 	0			0 If none of the items of the above list published 1 If one of the items of the above list published 2 If two of the items of the above list published 3 If more than two of the items of the above list published
05	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers given such opportunity in last two years- 5 ○ No such opportunity given X 			2	0 Observation tour not conducted 1 Less than 25% of the teachers got opportunities

						<p>in such activities</p> <p>2 25 to 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities</p> <p>3 More than 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities</p>
06	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the learning materials for regular study for the teachers (e.g., newspaper, journal, magazine) X Daily...X magazine/newspaper...X., monthly...X., half yearly...X, ○ Not managed 	0			<p>0 None of such materials managed</p> <p>1 Regularity of at least one of such materials</p> <p>2 Regularity of at least two of such materials</p> <p>3 Regularity of more than two of such materials</p>
07	Encouragement/Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teachers getting prize or reward for giving excellent result in his/her subject in last two years- 1 ○ Criteria of their selection- Best result 		2		<p>0 No such management by SMC</p> <p>1 Such policy has been formed but not implemented</p> <p>2 Such policy has been formed and at least one teacher has been rewarded</p> <p>3 Such policy has been formed and more than one</p>

							teacher has been rewarded
Total-21			9				

Table 2: TPD Performance Evaluation of School B

S N	Indicators of TPD	Detail of TPD activities performed in the school	TPD level/ School score				Criteria of TPD level/standard determination
			0	1	2	3	
01	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teachers' participation on training for PD ✓ ○ Conduction of training and workshop ✓ ○ Opportunity for further education (study leave, non-payment leave etc.) X ○ Visit to other schools ✓ ○ Research in group or individual X ○ Learning materials for PD, their regularity and study X ○ Meeting and discussion of the subject teachers ✓ ○ Writing and publication related to PD X 			2		0 None of the activities of the list performed 1 At least one of the activities performed 2 Two to four of the activities performed 3 More than four of the activities performed
02	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers involved in constructive work-8 			2		0 If none of the teachers involved

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Detail of the constructive work (e.g., seminar ✓, workshop ✓, project work ✓, journal X, magazine X, article writing X, subject teacher committee ✓) 					<p>1 If less than 25% of the teachers involved</p> <p>2 If 25 to 50% of the teachers involved</p> <p>3 If more than 50% of the teachers involved</p>
03	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teacher involved in Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school last year -7 ○ Not organized 			2		<p>0 Not organized</p> <p>1 Less than 25% of the teachers involved in such activities</p> <p>2 25 to 50% of the teachers involved in such activities</p> <p>3 More than 50% of the teachers involved in such activities</p>
04	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine published by the school in last two years X ○ Not published 	0				<p>0 If none of the items of the above list published</p> <p>1 If one of the items of the above list published</p> <p>2 If two of the items of the above list published</p> <p>3 If more than two of the items of the above list published</p>
05	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers given such opportunity in last two years X 	0				0 Observation tour not conducted

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ No such opportunity given 				<p>1 Less than 25% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities</p> <p>2 25 to 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities</p> <p>3 More than 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities</p>
06	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the learning materials for regular study for the teachers (e.g., newspaper, journal, magazine) X Daily X magazine/newspaper- X monthly-X, half yearly-X, ○ Not managed 	0			<p>0 None of such materials managed</p> <p>1 Regularity of at least one of such materials</p> <p>2 Regularity of at least two of such materials</p> <p>3 Regularity of more than two of such materials</p>

07	Encouragement/Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teachers getting prize or reward for giving excellent result in his/her subject in last two years-X ○ Criteria of their selection... 	0				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 No such management by SMC 1 Such policy has been formed but not implemented 2 Such policy has been formed and at least one teacher has been rewarded 3 Such policy has been formed and more than one teacher has been rewarded
Total-21			6				

Table 3: TPD Performance Evaluation of School C

S N	Indicators of TPD	Detail of TPD activities performed in the school	TPD level/ School score				Criteria of TPD level/standard determination
			0	1	2	3	
01	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teachers' participation on training for PD ✓ ○ Conduction of training and workshop ✓ ○ Opportunity for further education (study leave, non-payment leave etc.) X ○ Visit to other schools ○ Research in group or individual X ○ Learning materials for PD, their regularity and study X 			2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 None of the activities of the list performed 1 At least one of the activities performed 2 Two to four of the activities performed 3 More than four of the activities performed

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Meeting and discussion of the subject teachers ✓ ○ Writing and publication related to PD X 				
02	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers involved in constructive work- 3 ○ Detail of the constructive work (e.g., seminar ✓, workshop ✓, project work ✓, journal X, magazine X, article writing X, subject teacher committee ✓) 		1		<p>0 If none of the teachers involved</p> <p>1 If less than 25% of the teachers involved</p> <p>2 If 25 to 50% of the teachers involved</p> <p>3 If more than 50% of the teachers involved</p>
03	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teacher involved in Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school last year-2 ○ Not organized 		1		<p>0 Not organized</p> <p>1 Less than 25% of the teachers involved in such activities</p> <p>2 25 to 50% of the teachers involved in such activities</p> <p>3 More than 50% of the teachers involved in such activities</p>
04	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine published by the school in last two years X ○ Not published 	0			<p>0 If none of the items of the above list published</p> <p>1 If one of the items of the above list published</p> <p>2 If two of the items of the above list published</p> <p>3 If more than two of the items of the</p>

							above list published
05	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers given such opportunity in last two years X ○ No such opportunity given 	0				0 Observation tour not conducted 1 Less than 25% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities
06	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the learning materials for regular study for the teachers (e.g., newspaper, journal, magazine) X Daily X magazine/newspaper X monthly X, half yearly X, ○ Not managed 	0				0 None of such materials managed 1 Regularity of at least one of such materials 2 Regularity of at least two of such materials 3 Regularity of more than two of such materials

07	Encouragement/Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teachers getting prize or reward for giving excellent result in his/her subject in last two years X ○ Criteria of their selection... 	0				<p>0 No such management by SMC</p> <p>1 Such policy has been formed but not implemented</p> <p>2 Such policy has been formed and at least one teacher has been rewarded</p> <p>3 Such policy has been formed and more than one teacher has been rewarded</p>
Total-21				4			

Table 4: TPD Performance Evaluation of School D

S N	Indicators of TPD	Detail of TPD activities performed in the school	TPD level/ School score				Criteria of TPD level/standard determination
			0	1	2	3	
01	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Teachers' participation on training for PD √ ○ Conduction of training and workshop √ ○ Opportunity for further education (study leave, non-payment leave etc.) X ○ Visit to other schools ○ Research in group or individual X ○ Learning materials for PD, their regularity and study X 			2		<p>0 None of the activities of the list performed</p> <p>1 At least one of the activities performed</p> <p>2 Two to four of the activities performed</p> <p>3 More than four of the activities performed</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Meeting and discussion of the subject teachers √ ○ Writing and publication related to PD X 				
02	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers involved in constructive work-3 ○ Detail of the constructive work (e.g., seminar √, workshop √, project work √, journal X, magazine X, article writing X, subject teacher committee √) 			2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 If none of the teachers involved 1 If less than 25% of the teachers involved 2 If 25 to 50% of the teachers involved 3 If more than 50% of the teachers involved
03	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teacher involved in Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school last year 1 ○ Not organized 		1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 Not organized 1 Less than 25% of the teachers involved in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers involved in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers involved in such activities
04	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine published by the school in last two years X ○ Not published 	0			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 If none of the items of the above list published 1 If one of the items of the above list published 2 If two of the items of the above list published 3 If more than two of the items of the

							above list published
05	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers given such opportunity in last two years-1 ○ No such opportunity given 		1			0 Observation tour not conducted 1 Less than 25% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities
06	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the learning materials for regular study for the teachers (e.g., newspaper, journal, magazine) X Daily X magazine/newspaper X monthly X, half yearly X, ○ Not managed 	0				0 None of such materials managed 1 Regularity of at least one of such materials 2 Regularity of at least two of such materials 3 Regularity of more than two of such materials

07	Encouragement/Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teachers getting prize or reward for giving excellent result in his/her subject in last two years X ○ Criteria of their selection... 	0				<p>0 No such management by SMC</p> <p>1 Such policy has been formed but not implemented</p> <p>2 Such policy has been formed and at least one teacher has been rewarded</p> <p>3 Such policy has been formed and more than one teacher has been rewarded</p>
Total-21				6			

The Table 1,2,3,and 4 above present the TPD performance of the four schools: school A, school B, school C, and school D respectively. Particularly, the seven TPD indicators used, and the detail of the activities performed by the schools have shown in the Tables. The criteria of TPD standard determination have been elaborated in the last column. More importantly, the scores of the four schools on the basis of their performance have been presented in the four Tables each.

It can be understand from the Tables that the schools were relatively more able to perform the activities such as participating in the training and workshops, involving in further education, and participating in meetings and discussions related to PD. Table 1 shows that school A relatively stronger to perform the activities such as conducting constructive works, managing observational tours, and rewarding the best performer teachers, while it was weak in the activities such as making publication, managing learning materials for PD, and organizing capacity building training. Likewise, schools B and D were relatively stronger to organize capacity building training, but they were weak to perform other activities above, and also to conduct

Table 5: School score and TPD standard of the schools

TPD Sub- aspect	TPD indicators, Full marks and Criteria of TPD standard determination			School score and TPD standard of the schools			
	TPD indicators	Full marks	Total full marks and criteria	School	School Score	TPD standard	
TPD	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	3	Total full marks: 21	School A	9 42.85%	General	
	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	3	Criteria: 0-7 Weak, 8-14 General, 15-17 Medium, 18-21 Excellent	School B	6 28.57%	Weak	
	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	3		School C	4 19.04%	Weak	
	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	3		School D	6 28.57%	Weak	
	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	3					
	Management and regularity of learning materials for PD	3					
	Encouragement/Reward	3					

Observational tours, and to encourage/reward the teachers. School C was more weaker to perform all such activities above, though it seemed to be relatively stronger to organize observational tour in comparison to schools B and D.

Table 5 shows the school scores and TPD standard of the schools based on the evaluation. It also includes the TPD indicators, their full marks, and the criteria of the standard determination. More specifically, it shows the score of four schools. The Table indicates that school A has relatively better TPD standard, the score is 9, out of 21 full marks, the school achieved 42.85%. School B and D have equal standard in terms of their TPD performance.

These schools' score is 6, i.e., 28.57% achievement. School C has poorest performance among the four schools. Its score is 4, i. e., 19.04% achievement. According to the criteria established, school A has 'general' TPD standard, and all other three schools have weak TPD standard.

Opportunities and Challenge of TPD

This section deals with the opportunities and challenges that the teachers encountered in the process of their professional development. It includes the qualitative analysis and interpretation of the of the teachers' opinions regarding the open ended questions concerned with the opportunities and challenges of TPD.

Opportunities to the Teachers

Professional development of the teacher was given highest priority in SSRP 2009-2015. The main goal was to ensure that all teachers have the knowledge and skills required to effectively facilitate student learning processes (MOE, 2009). SSRP planned the increment in the minimum qualifications of the teachers and mandatory training requirements and regular updates. The participants' experience regarding opportunities created by TPD plan have been discussed and interpreted in the sub-headings below.

Teacher Training and Workshop. The participants had positive attitude towards TPD training and workshops. Such activities provided them with new knowledge, refreshment and updates to recent trends. One of the participants opined,

TPD training and workshops are a good opportunity for us to learn and share the skills and knowledge which can contribute for making our teaching more effective. It also provides us with an environment to discuss among the group members about the useful techniques and materials essential for teaching.

The teachers shared their experiences that the teacher with TPD training at least understand the relationship among the curriculum, text-book, and teacher's guide. They also have some knowledge and importance of learner centered methods and techniques such as task-based and project-based methods; and discussion, role-play. The teachers' belief is that TPD has improved the students learning achievement as well.

In fact, TPD is a continuous process that has broadly two aspects: teacher training, and teacher development. Training of the teacher includes mainly 'what aspect' (content) and, 'how aspect' (methodology and technology). Thus, TPD training provides the teachers with the ideas of the effective delivery of contents associating them with appropriate pedagogy and technology. This knowledge, to Koehler and Mishra (2013), the TPCK (technological pedagogical content knowledge), is a good benefit of TPD training and workshops to the teachers.

Supporting Materials. Providing the schools with the teaching materials and other supplementary materials is another important advantage of TPD programme. The government, under the Ministry of Education, has prioritized preparation and producing the essential teaching materials such as text books, reference books, teacher guides, and many other visual and audio-visual materials. Besides, preparation and collection of teaching-learning materials is one of the main components of TPD training package. This not only encourages and strengthens the ideas of preparation of teaching materials but also develops their skills of their effective use.

In addition, the essential teaching-learning technological equipment such as Desktop, Laptops, Projectors, Smartboards, CDs and VCDs are being made available to the schools. Use of such technological equipment has contributed to improve the quality of education. One of the participants opined,

The teaching materials and other modern technologies have been useful for effective delivery of the contents and concepts. They help attract students' attention to the lesson, and increase their level of motivation. They also help make the classroom environment more interactive. This certainly makes students' learning more permanent.

Availability of the teaching-learning materials and their appropriate use in the teaching-learning activity is one of the essential aspects of quality education. Realizing this fact, TPD programme has emphasized using teaching materials and modern technologies in the teaching-learning activities.

Subject Committee Discussion. Subject committee meeting, one of the components of TPD programme, is very important activity for advancing teacher quality. It is a group discussion in which they can discuss about their problems, confusions and the methods and techniques of teaching and learning. They also can interact about effective delivery of subject matter exchanging their ideas about making good lesson plans and preparing and collecting essential teaching materials. The most important advantage is that the experienced teachers share their teaching experiences and the novel teachers can exchange their ideas of current trends and concepts. Both experienced and novel teachers can be benefitted from subject committee discussions.

In this study, the participants viewed that they found subject committee meeting much beneficial. One of the teachers opined, "Subject committee discussion is very useful for me because I can learn the solution of many of my confusions and problems that appear while handling the text-book". "We can exchange our teaching experiences about methods and materials, and get into the best solution for effective teaching" another of the participants expressed.

Subject committee meeting is mainly important for sharing ideas and exchanging resources. The discussion can be a very good collaborative activity for the tasks such as carrying out action research and project work, writing articles, organizing seminars or

workshops, and for publication of their articles, journals or bulletins. This can be utilized as the opportunities for enhancing their creativity and dissemination of their experiences and knowledge.

Challenges/Difficulties

The participants shared their experiences that there were many challenges and difficulties they encountered during the TPD process. The difficulties they experienced were mainly related to the implications of the ideas and knowledge into the classroom environment, TPD training and workshops, and availability of supplementary materials. These have been discussed below in brief.

Implementation of Knowledge and Skills Gained. One of the major difficulties that the teachers encountered was that there were many problems in the implementation of the knowledge and skills they learn in the training and workshops. The classroom context was not favorable for them so as to apply the methods or techniques they practice in the training. One of the teachers commented, “We learn knowledge and skills in the training and workshops, but our classroom environment is quite different and difficult to apply the skills and knowledge we learn”. They argued that the availability of the tools and materials, class size, work load given to the teachers, and students’ level knowledge are some of the major factors that influence their teaching activities.

They shared that the teaching materials such as maps, posters, charts, pictures, flashcards, are not available in adequate number, and that the modern tools such laptops, projectors, smartboards are not available in many of the schools. Likewise, in many of the schools, the size of the class was quite large to conduct student centered and more interactive techniques such as role play, discussion, and group work activities. It was also that the teachers were compelled to teach seven periods a day which made them too tired to teach more energetically and actively in all the periods. The work load given to the teachers was also a main problem that influenced the quality of teachers’ preparation for the class and their presentation. Moreover, many of students in most of the schools do not have required basic knowledge to carry out the tasks and projects to be conducted.

TPD Training and Workshops. The participants were not satisfied with the TPD training they participated. They shared their experiences that they often did not find the contents of TPD training based on their needs or demand. One of the teachers opined,

The training programmes are not so satisfactory in that they are often not need based. The trainers come with a training package designed somewhere which in many respects, do not address our demands/needs. It is also that we do not find many of the theories, and methods discuss in the training are far from the classroom contexts.

The excerpt above indicate that the TPD training programmes were fruitful for enhancing the teachers’ personal knowledge and skills, They, however, were not advantageous form their classroom implementation points of view because many of the techniques and

methods they discuss in the training sessions have been developed/ designed in foreign contexts. It was also that of training course have been designed to be conducted their continuity in different phases, but the training programmes have not been organized in a certain regular interval. This has created difficulties in recalling the previously learnt ideas, and link them with present learning.

Availability and Use of Supplementary Materials. The participants opined that the supporting teaching-learning materials available to the schools were quite inadequate. The teachers use only the textbooks and duster and chalk (recently, marker in some schools), and they do not think of using other supplementary materials due to two main factors: lack of time for preparing/collecting them, and lack of supervision of their classes. Many of the teachers have not developed their habit of making a collection of the teaching materials for his/her subject, and it is often very difficult for a teacher who need to teach seven periods a day to prepare or collect a box/bag of teaching materials that s/he needs every day. It is also that there is neither any provision of any regular and/or occasional class observation (by peer, Headmaster, or school supervisor), nor is there any system developed for punishing and/or encouraging the teacher/s who make/s an effort in such activities.

The participants were not quite satisfied with the way that the supplementary materials were distributed. One of the teachers reacted,

It is the responsibility of the Government to make the needed teaching materials available to the schools. What we get in most of the schools is only the textbook. We neither get the books in time nor is there any equality in the distribution of other supporting materials, only a few schools have been supported with such materials.

The Headmasters opined that lack of budget was the main cause affecting the management of supporting teaching materials. A few model schools have been supported with certain amount for purchasing teaching-learning tools and materials. This inequality in the distribution of the supplementary materials have created a negative effect towards using supplementary materials in the classroom. In fact, only a few of the schools have access to the modern technological tools such as laptops, projectors, smart boards etc, and still the teachers and the students in many of the schools listen about such tools as a story. More importantly, such tools have not been utilized properly in the schools where some of these tools have been made available due to lack of technological knowledge of the teachers. The teachers were not provided opportunities to take part in the training programmes that are concerned with the pedagogical use of such modern tools and technologies.

Publications and Observational Tours. One of the important difficulties to the teachers was publication of the journals and making observational tours. The teachers shared their experiences that there were mainly two types of problems that affect such activities of publications. The first was they lack time to engage in research and writing. It was because they were over loaded, and they needed to spend most of their time in preparation of the lessons

and teaching the students. The second reason was that they lacked financial support to make such publications.

Observational tours are also of great advantageous among TPD activities to the teachers. Such programmes provide the teachers with practical experiences of school administration and teaching-learning activities. However, different schools have different physical and academic contexts which makes them difficult to apply the ideas they learn in the observation. One of the teachers opined,

I once got opportunity to visit one of the model schools in my local level. I learnt many ideas there about school administration, classroom management, and classroom teaching. However, the problem is that I do not find any favorable context/environment in my school so as to apply the ideas I learnt.

In addition, the problem of financial support also influenced in their organization of observational tours. Therefore, such programmes have been very rarely organized by the schools. There was also that such observations have not been effective as they often lack experts to give suggestive feedback analyzing the events or activities they observe.

CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section mainly includes the summary and the conclusion of the study. Based on the findings and conclusion, it also deals with the recommendations made by the researcher in the study.

Summary

Teacher Professional development, one of the key factors for ensuring quality education, is the major target of most of the educational institutions. It is a continuous process that brings ongoing changes in the quality of teachers, and increases the teachers' knowledge, skills, and expertise that make them professional. TPD is supposed to be a key factor for making improvement in classroom pedagogy. Realizing this, MOE has made TPD mandatory in the community schools in Nepal. Several plans, policies, and programmes have been implemented and quite a large amount of budget has been invested for TPD in the secondary schools in Nepal. This study attempts to explore the effect of such investment. Particularly, it attempts to explore the present status or the TPD standard of the secondary schools; and the opportunities and challenges for the teachers in their TPD process.

The study site in this research was Menchhyayem rural municipality of Terhathum district, situated in the eastern part of Nepal. All the four secondary schools of Menchhyayem municipality were taken as the sample schools. The headmaster and the senior secondary school teacher from each of those schools were the participants. This study adopted constructivists' research paradigm and qualitative research design. Observation and semi structured interview were the research methods used, and observation check list and interview questionnaire were used as the research tools. The observational check list was filled in with the help of the Headmaster of each schools, and semi structure interviews were conducted with the most senior teacher of each schools. The quantitative data were presented in the tables, and were analyzed descriptively, while the qualitative data were analyzed thematically.

It was found in the study that the TPD status of the secondary school was not satisfactory. Out of the four sample schools, none of the schools had excellent standard, they did not have even medium standard. Only one of them had general standard, and all other had weak standard. Particularly, the schools were relatively stronger to perform the activities such as participating in training and workshops, being involved in further study, and conducting constructive works such as conducting extra- curricular activities and managing extra classes. On the other hand, they were weak to perform the activities such as publishing, managing learning materials for research work, and managing observational tours. Likewise, the teachers found that they got a good opportunities for training and support for class materials. They also took lots of benefits from subject teachers meeting and discussions. On the other hand, they had to tackle with the difficulties in the implementation of the ideas or skills they learnt due to several factors such as poor infrastructure development, and level of the students' knowledge.

Not all training programmes used to be need-based, and that they lacked adequate fund for conducting different educational programmes and managing supporting learning materials for their professional development.

Conclusion

TPD, a continuous process of the capacity building of the teachers, is an important requisite of quality education. TPD can be evaluated on the basis of several indicators such as teacher training, teacher qualification, workshops and seminars, journal publication, observational tours, students learning achievements and so on. In this study it was found that TPD programme created both opportunities and challenges to the teachers. It gave some advantages to the schools and teachers, though they were not complete satisfactory. Opportunities of training and workshops for updating and refreshing themselves, sharing and exchanging ideas and teaching-learning resources among teachers, discussion and collaboration with the experts were some of the major advantages of TPD programme. On the other hand, difficulties in the implementation of the knowledge and skills, inadequate teaching-learning materials and technological tools in the schools, and lack of financial support were some of the major challenges. Because of such factors, most of the schools had weak TPD status, and that none of the schools had excellent standard. Remarkably, they did not have even medium standard. The concerned authority need to be more responsible and sincere to make improvements in such situation.

Recommendations

No doubt, TPD is essential for improving quality education. In context of Nepal, however, the TPD status of the secondary school seems to be in weak condition. Though the teachers have been able to take some benefits of the TPD programme, they are tackling several difficulties in their TPD process. This study has made following recommendations for the betterment of this situation. Realizing the importance of TPD, reality-based plans and strategies need to be implemented.

The infrastructure of the secondary school need to be improved.

Training programmes should be need-based.

Budget to be allocated to education should be increased.

Reality-based monitoring of the secondary schools is essential.

There must be provision for reward and punishment to the teachers.

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APPENDICES

Appendix-A

Observation Checklist (adapted from ERO, 2020)

School:

Total number of teachers:

TPD Activities and Criteria of TPD Score Determination

S N	Indicators of TPD	Detail of TPD activities in the school	TPD level/ School score				Criteria of TPD level/score determination
			0	1	2	3	
01	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tick on the appropriate option/s ○ Teachers' participation on training for PD ○ Conduction of training and workshop ○ Opportunity for further education (study leave, non-payment leave etc.) ○ Visit to other schools ○ Research in group or individual ○ Learning materials for PD, their regularity and study ○ Meeting and discussion of the subject teachers ○ Writing and publication related to PD 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 None of the activities of the list performed 1 At least one of the activities performed 2 Two to four of the activities performed 3 More than four of the activities performed
02	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers involved in constructive work ○ Detail of the constructive work (e.g., seminar, workshop, project work, journal, magazine, article writing, subject teacher committee) 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 If none of the teachers involved 1 If less than 25% of the teachers involved 2 If 25 to 50% of the teachers involved 3 If more than 50% of the

							teachers involved
03	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teacher involved in Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school last year.... ○ Not organized 					0 Not organized 1 Less than 25% of the teachers involved in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers involved in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers involved in such activities
04	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine published by the school in last two years ○ Not published 					0 If none of the items of the above list published 1 If one of the items of the above list published 2 If two of the items of the above list published 3 If more than two of the items of the above list published
05	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the teachers given such opportunity in last two years ○ No such opportunity given 					0 Observation tour not conducted 1 Less than 25% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities 2 25 to 50% of the teachers got

						opportunities in such activities 3 More than 50% of the teachers got opportunities in such activities
06	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of the learning materials for regular study for the teachers (e.g., newspaper, journal, magazine) Daily... magazine/newspaper...., monthly....., half yearly...., ○ Not managed 				0 None of such materials managed 1 Regularity of at least one of such materials 2 Regularity of at least two of such materials 3 Regularity of more than two of such materials
07	Encouragement/Reward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number of teachers getting prize or reward for giving excellent result in his/her subject in last two years ○ Criteria of their selection... 				0 No such management by SMC 1 Such policy has been formed but not implemented 2 Such policy has been formed and at least one teacher has been rewarded 3 Such policy has been formed and more than one teacher has been rewarded
Total-21						

Appendix-B

Criteria of TPD standard determination (adapted from ERO, 2020)

TPD Sub-aspect	TPD indicators and Total Full marks			Criteria of TPD standard determination	
	TPD indicators	Full marks	Total full marks	Score	TPD standard
Teacher Professional Development	Measures implemented for TPD in the school	3	21	0-7	Weak
	Constructive works related to TPD and Teaching-Learning	3		7-14	General
	Capacity building training and resource class organized by the school	3		15-18	Medium
	Publication of memorandum, bulletin, magazine, or wall magazine	3		19-21	Excellent
	Observation tour (Tour to other school, or to the schools of the area)	3			
	Management and regularity of the learning materials for PD	3			
	Encouragement/Reward	3			
Extra/co-curricular activities			18	0-6	Weak
				7-12	General
				13-16	Medium
				17-18	Excellent

Appendix-C

Interview Questionnaire

Please give your opinion being related to the following questions,

- 1) Have you been involved in TPD activities? If yes, for how long?
- 2) Have you taken TPD training? If yes, what is your general impression towards TPD training? Please share your experience.
- 3) What is your experience regarding the implementation of knowledge you gain during training and workshop into the classroom?
- 4) What sorts of TPD supporting materials are available in your school?
- 5) Have you involved in any TPD related workshop/seminar? What is your experience about such programme?
- 6) What TPD activities are you impressed with?
- 7) What are the challenges/difficulties you encounter in the TPD process?
- 8) What is your suggestion for the betterment of TPD?